

Thomson coil equivalent electrical circuit model and identification of parameters

Dragan Jovicic
School of Engineering
University of Aberdeen
Aberdeen, AB24 3UE, UK
d.jovicic@abdn.ac.uk

Ibrahim A. Shehu
School of Engineering
University of Aberdeen
Aberdeen, AB24 3UE, UK
ibrahim.shehu@abdn.ac.uk

Abstract—Thomson coils (TCs) are becoming preferred drivers for all high/medium voltage DC Circuit Breakers (DC CB), yet accurate and convenient TC models are lacking. This study presents an equivalent circuit model that represents the TC with an LR circuit for the coil, another LR circuit for the armature and a shunt magnetizing branch represented by a gap-dependent inductance L_m .

TC parameters can be measured only indirectly as lump impedance using frequency-dependent inductive and resistive measurements at the coil terminals. A wide range of measurements of inductance and resistance for test TC is presented across different frequencies and for 8 disk positions. The magnetizing branch and disk parameters are included in the proposed model in a form that differs from the conventional transformer model. The TC electrical circuit model is represented as a transfer function, linking coil voltage and current to enable comparison with experimental measurements.

Verification against measurements on a TC used with medium voltage DC CB shows reasonably good matching for a range of disk distances (0-6 mm) and across a wide frequency band for both magnitude and phase. It is further demonstrated that the transformer T-model cannot adequately capture the essential gap dependence, whereas the proposed model is suitable candidate for system-level studies of DC CB actuators.

Keywords—DC Circuit Breakers, Thomson coil, Magnetic circuit model,

I. INTRODUCTION

DC circuit breakers (DC CB) have been studied in a wide range of Medium and High Voltage applications [1]-[3], and they have been implemented at several projects in China, including the 500 kV, 8 GW Zhangbei Chinese DC grid [4].

All DC CBs utilise Thomson coil (TC) as the driving mechanism, because of requirements for very fast opening. Modelling of Thomson coils is challenging because they consist of two coupled circuits: the coil and the disk. Identification of disk parameters and mutual inductance are difficult since no direct measurements are possible.

While the theory of coupled coils enables calculation of self and mutual inductance for given geometries [5],[6],[7], existing studies are mainly focused on communication applications at low power and high frequency, and thus do not provide a suitable circuit model for the TC.

Thomson coil for HV DC CB has been modelled using several fundamentally different approaches:

- As equivalent mutual inductance L_m in [8] and [9].
- In [10] and [11] it is represented as equivalent LR circuit.

- A single frequency-dependent equivalent inductor combining both coil and disk is employed in [12].
- Another approach is to represent Thomson drive as 2 series-connected LR impedances (one for coil and another for the disk) [13]. This model was demonstrated to be accurate, but it employs detailed Multiphysics COMSOL finite-element model for mutual inductance and disk, which is very tedious and time consuming.

The TC model verification in all the above studies is done indirectly. Usually only the circuit variables are measured (supply voltage and coil current) or disk position, which assumes that force generation model is included and this introduces further uncertainty. These test have limited accuracy since TC parameters have not been directly identified, analysed or verified.

In the present study, we aim developing electrical circuit model for TC which includes all key parameters from the coupled magnetic and electrical circuits. We will perform verification against thorough frequency-dependent impedance measurements for a range of disk positions using a representative test Thomson coil.

II. TEST COIL AND MEASUREMENTS

A. Test system

Fig. 1a) shows the Thomson coil under test, which was used in earlier projects on DC CB [3], and described in [14]. The coil wire is of copper and the holder is made of steel, while disk is of aluminium. The dimensions are given in TABLE II. in the Appendix. Disk would normally be connected with a rod that drives contacts in DC Circuit Breaker. When external power source is discharged through coil, a large current is generated in the disk which creates repelling force with the coil current [8]-[13].

The plan for the study is to measure impedance at the coil connecting terminals, and then develop detailed model of the system that will give same responses at the corresponding points in the model.

B. Measurements

Coil impedance can be readily measured with an impedance meter. Since disk parameters cannot be measured, it is postulated that their impact can be reflected indirectly in measuring coil impedance at different disk positions. We used an Agilent 35670A Dynamic Signal Analyzer (DSA) to measure the resistive and inductive components at the coil terminals, over a range of frequencies (50 Hz -20 kHz) and for 7 different distances between coil and disk (0 mm – 6 mm in 1 mm increments). It is known that the force on the TC is generated within the first 0.1-0.5 ms after trip [13], and the

gap distance achieved in this period will be few mm [3][13]. Fig. 1b) shows the experimental setup with a micrometre for adjusting the gap distance. We also measured the impedance when the disk is removed, and all measurements are shown in TABLE III. in the Appendix.

Several important conclusions can be drawn:

- Expectedly, inductance reduces as frequency is increasing, but this may not be represented in any lumped-parameter model.
- Inductance significantly depends on disk position. It is seen that impedance increases as distance is increasing. This is not intuitive conclusion, since mutual inductance reduces with distance (reluctance increases). However, this is a known phenomenon [13]: as distance is increasing, the counter-effect of the disk's inductance (and resistance) is reducing, leading to higher measured inductance.
- Resistance increases significantly with frequency. This is primarily due to the skin effect, but partly also to the system topology (coupling between inductances). This also can not be represented in any model using lumped constant parameters.
- Resistance changes as distance is changing at each particular frequency. This is caused by the change in coupling with the disk, which includes a resistive component.

a) Thomson coil under testing.

b) Measuring TC parameters at different disk distance

Fig. 1. Testing thomson coil (coil and disk) parameters.

III. THOMSON COIL EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT MODEL

Fig. 2a) shows the proposed equivalent circuit model for the Thomson coil. It includes:

- Coil circuit, represented by leakage/parasitics L_c, R_c , coil magnetising voltage V_{mcoil} and external voltage V_e .
- Armature circuit, which includes a shorted parasitic circuit L_a, R_a , and an armature magnetising voltage V_{marm} .

The initial approach in modelling the magnetising voltages was to use the “transformer T model” with a shunt-connected L_m as shown in Fig. 2b), and similar model is used in [8] and [9]. However, this approach did not give good matching with measurements as illustrated in Section VI. The problem with this method is that L_m significantly depends on the distance between disk and coil, but the magnetising component caused by local current does not depend on distance as flux path is essentially in non-magnetic material.

The proposed model for the magnetizing branch is shown Fig. 2c). Here, the magnetising voltage depends solely on the derivative of the current in the coupling (opposite) circuit.

A 3rd order corresponding transfer function model is developed in MATLAB code (and provided in Appendix II), for both the proposed model and the transformer model. The models take the external voltage V_e as input and the coil current I_c as output to enable comparisons with experimental measurements in TABLE III.

Fig. 2. Thomson coil equivalent circuit model with magnetising voltages.

IV. MUTUAL INDUCTANCE

Mutual inductance L_m in the TC-disk system cannot be directly measured, but can be calculated using expressions for the inductance of two planar coils, derived from Maxwell's equations [5][6]:

$$L_m = (N_c N_d / (2N + 1)^2) \sum_{j=-N:N} \sum_{i=N:N} M(ij) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$M(ij) = (2\mu_0 \sqrt{R(i)R(j)}) / k(ij) [(1 - (k^2(ij)/2))K(k(ij)) - E(k(ij))] \\ R(i) = R_d + (b_d / (2N + 1))i, R_d = (R_{2d} + R_{1d})/2, b_d = R_{2d} - R_{1d}, \\ R(j) = R_c + (b_c / (2N + 1))j, R_c = (R_{2c} + R_{1c})/2, b_c = R_{2c} - R_{1c}, \\ k^2(ij) = (4 R(i)R(j)) / [(R(i) + R(j))^2 + z^2] \quad (2)$$

R_1, R_2 are the inner and outer radii of coil/disk with c/d index (TABLE II), $b_{c/d}$ is the radial width of coil/disk, z is the axial distance between the coil and disk, $N_{c/d}$ is the total number of turns in the coil/disk, N defines how many filament elements are considered in coil/disk ($N=100$), $K(k(ij))$ $E(k(ij))$ are the complete elliptical integral of the first and second kind with modulus k , and $\mu_m = \mu_r \mu_0$, with μ_r relative permeability and $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m is the permeability of free space.

Fig. 3 shows the calculated values for the magnetising inductance for a range of distances. In our TC, we have steel holder for the coil, which somewhat impacts the effective permeability of the medium in the flux path, while all the above formulae (1)-(2) assume a homogenous flux path. Therefore, we have modified the permeability in the model by assuming a small percentage of steel with $\mu_r=50$, and Fig. 3 shows 3 curves for 0%, 3% and 5% steel in the flux path. The verification section demonstrates that 3% steel gives the best matching.

The L_m curve from Fig. 3 is recorded as a look-up table and called within the main MATLAB file for calculations at the required disk distance.

Fig. 3. Calculated mutual inductance.

V. COIL AND DISK LEAKAGE PARAMETERS

The coil parasitic inductance L_c and resistance R_c can be directly measured, and they correspond to the last column (infinity distance) in TABLE III. The leakage inductance is also calculated using the formula for planar coils from [7]:

$$L_c = (C_1 \mu_0 N_c^2 d_{avg} / 2) (\ln(C_2 / \gamma) + C_3 \gamma + C_4 \gamma^2) \quad (3)$$

where $d_{avg} = (R_2 + R_1)/2$, $\gamma = (R_2 - R_1)/(R_2 + R_1)$, N_c is the number of turns of coil, and C_1 to C_4 are layout-dependent coefficients given as $C_1 = 1$, $C_2 = 2.46$, $C_3 = 1$, $C_4 = 0.2$, for our coil layout (circle).

The resistance is calculated using the wire dimension (thickness $w \times$ height h), coil size (R_1, R_2), number of turns N_c , and copper specific resistivity (ρ):

$$R_c = \rho L / A = \rho (2\pi d_{avg} N_c) / (w \times h) \quad (4)$$

Since the disk leakage parameters cannot be measured, they are calculated using formulae (3) and (4) and assuming $N_d=1$. TABLE I. shows the calculated parameters. The measured coil parameters (at 2 kHz) are used, while calculated parameters are shown for completeness. It is seen that the measured inductance is different (larger), which is attributed to the impact of steel holder (which is in the disk flux path) and also since different frequency is assumed. The measured inductance at 20 kHz is 2.27 μ H (from TABLE III.), which is very close to the calculated value. The measured resistance is larger because of skin and proximity effects.

The core loss component did not have much impact on model accuracy, and a fixed value of $R_m = 1000 \Omega$ is employed.

TABLE I. PARASITIC INDUCTANCE AND RESISTANCE

		Inductance [μ H]	Resistance [$m\Omega$]
Coil	Measured (2 kHz)	3.5	14.18
	Calculated	2.23	2.8
Disk calculated		0.0188	0.11

VI. MODEL VERIFICATION

A. Dependence on distance

Fig. 4 shows the model comparison with measured values for different gap distances, at frequency of 2 kHz. It includes 4 modelling approaches: RL circuit, Equivalent L, transformer model, and the proposed model. The equivalent RL and L models use the single measured values of R_c and L_c at 0 mm gap, and at the adopted frequency (2 kHz).

It is seen that the proposed model gives best matching with measurements and importantly, only this model predicts the increase in inductance with increasing gap distance. The matching of the resistive component is of less concern since skin effect plays significant role, which is not accounted in any of the models. Also, in the external circuit, it is usually the inductive TC component that has significantly larger impact [13]. The transformer model, in contrast, does not show correct inductance change as gap is changing.

Fig. 5 shows that matching is better at 10 kHz, while similar results are observed at lower frequencies.

B. Dependence on frequency

Fig. 6 shows the Bode plot over the frequency range 50 Hz-20 kHz, for a fixed gap of 1 mm, where the equivalent parameters are taken at 2 kHz. Firstly, it is concluded that TC responds similarly as a 1st order system (-20 dB slope and -90^o phase), even though it is a 3rd order system.

It is observed that the proposed model gives the best overall matching in both magnitude and phase. This makes it particularly suitable for dynamic studies of the TC in external electrical circuits, including cases where the mechanical system dynamics (gap variation) must be considered. In contrast, the transformer model underestimates the magnitude by 5-8 dB and the phase by approximately 10^o. The simple RL model provides accuracy only at the specific frequency and gap where its parameters are extracted. Similarly, the Equivalent L model is only accurate at a single frequency-gap combination.

a) Resistive component

b) Inductive component

Fig. 4. Comparison of models and measurements at 2 kHz.

a) Resistive component

b) Inductive component

Fig. 5. Comparison of models and measurements at 10 kHz.

a) Magnitude

b) Phase

Fig. 6. Bode plot comparison of model and measurements at 1 mm gap.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This study proposed and verified an equivalent circuit model for the Thomson coil that captures the interaction between the coil and disk with a gap-dependent shunt magnetising branch. Unlike the classic transformer and simplified RL models, the proposed model correctly reproduces the inductance variation with gap distance.

It was shown that while coil parameters can be measured directly, the influence of the disk and magnetising effects can be inferred indirectly from terminal impedance measurements across frequency and gap distance. Comparison with experimental measurements showed that the proposed model achieves good matching in both magnitude and phase over a considered frequency range.

The results indicate that the proposed model provides an accurate representation of the TC in its essential dynamic range. This makes it well suited for integration into broader system-level simulations of DC CB actuators, where coupled electrical and mechanical dynamics must be accurately captured.

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APPENDIX I. Thomson coil and disk data

TABLE II. THOMSON COIL PARAMETERS

Material	<i>Coil</i>	<i>Disk</i>
	Copper (2.75x1.4 mm) Steel holder of 25 mm radius.	Aluminum
Outer radius (R ₂)	21 mm	25 mm
Inner radius (R ₁)	6.5 mm	0
Thickness (w)	2.75 mm	4.5 mm
Height (h)	1.4 mm	7 mm
Number of turns (N)	9	1

APPENDIX II. Transfer function model of transformer and proposed models

A. Transformer model 3rd order transfer function

$$1/Z_{eq1}(s) = (a_2 \cdot s^2 + a_1 \cdot s + a_0) / (b_3 \cdot s^3 + b_2 \cdot s^2 + b_1 \cdot s + b_0);$$

where:

$$a_2 = L_m \cdot L_{larm}, \quad a_1 = L_m \cdot R_{arm} + L_{larm} \cdot R_{core}, \quad a_0 = R_{core} \cdot R_{arm}$$

$$b_3 = (L_{lc} + N \cdot L_m) \cdot L_m \cdot L_{larm}$$

$$b_2 = (L_{lc} + N \cdot L_m) \cdot (L_m \cdot R_{arm} + L_{larm} \cdot R_{core}) + R_c \cdot L_m \cdot R_{arm} - L_m^2 \cdot R_{core}$$

$$b_1 = (L_{lc} + N \cdot L_m) \cdot R_{core} \cdot R_{arm} + R_c \cdot (L_m \cdot R_{arm} + L_{larm} \cdot R_{core})$$

$$b_0 = R_c \cdot R_{core} \cdot R_{arm}$$

B. Proposed model 3rd order transfer function

$$1/Z_{eq2}(s) = (a_2 \cdot s^2 + a_1 \cdot s + a_0) / (b_3 \cdot s^3 + b_2 \cdot s^2 + b_1 \cdot s + b_0);$$

where:

$$a_2 = L_m \cdot L_{larm}, \quad a_1 = L_m \cdot R_{arm} + L_{larm} \cdot R_{core}, \quad a_0 = R_{core} \cdot R_{arm}$$

$$b_3 = L_{lc} \cdot L_m \cdot L_{larm}$$

$$b_2 = L_{lc} \cdot (L_m \cdot R_{arm} + L_{larm} \cdot R_{core}) + R_c \cdot L_m \cdot R_{arm} - L_m^2 \cdot R_{core}$$

$$b_1 = L_{lc} \cdot R_{core} \cdot R_{arm} + R_c \cdot (L_m \cdot R_{arm} + L_{larm} \cdot R_{core})$$

$$b_0 = R_c \cdot R_{core} \cdot R_{arm}$$

APPENDIX III. Thomson coil resistance and inductance measurements

TABLE III. THOMSON COIL INDUCTANCE AND RESISTANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR A RANGE OF GAP DISTANCES

Freq.	Distance of disk from coil															
	0mm		1mm		2mm		3mm		4mm		5mm		6mm		Infinity	
	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]	[μH]	[mΩ]
50 Hz	2.45	5.5	2.89	5.6	2.68	5.56	2.86	5.4	3.05	5.4	3.02	5.4	3.11	5.49	3.13	5.27
150 Hz	2.4	6.4	2.56	6.3	2.67	6.4	2.71	6.2	2.8	6.12	2.84	6.09	3.05	6.07	3.65	5.45
250 Hz	2.2	6.9	2.38	6.9	2.5	6.68	2.66	6.6	2.7	6.5	2.86	6.4	2.98	6.5	3.86	5.87
500 Hz	2.1	8	2.27	8.5	2.43	8.35	2.57	8.45	2.7	8.04	2.92	7.6	2.92	7.7	3.99	7.14
1 kHz	1.87	10.06	2.05	9.9	2.2	9.94	2.36	9.7	2.5	9.6	2.63	9.6	2.73	9.5	3.8	9.24
1.5 kHz	1.7	11.6	1.87	11.5	2.04	11.4	2.19	11.45	2.3	11.18	2.46	11.25	2.58	11.2	3.64	11.55
2 kHz	1.59	13	1.76	13.02	1.93	13.02	2.08	13	2.22	12.9	2.35	12.9	2.47	13	3.5	14.18
2.5 kHz	1.51	14.5	1.68	14.4	1.85	14.46	2	14.5	2.14	14.3	2.27	14.4	2.38	14.5	3.4	16.68
5 kHz	1.284	20.6	1.46	20.6	1.63	21	1.77	21.1	1.91	21.6	2.03	22	2.14	22.4	3.05	30
7 kHz	1.184	24.8	1.365	25.03	1.53	25.6	1.67	26.2	1.8	26.9	1.92	27.7	2.03	28.6	2.87	40.8
10 kHz	1.094	30.7	1.27	31.2	1.43	32.2	1.57	33.4	1.69	34.6	1.81	36.2	1.91	37.6	2.67	57
15 kHz	1.003	39.3	1.176	40.8	1.33	42.8	1.466	45.2	1.58	47.5	1.69	50.2	1.78	52.8	2.44	83.7
20 kHz	0.94	47.4	1.11	49.7	1.26	53	1.39	56.4	1.51	60.2	1.6	64	1.69	67.9	2.27	109.2

- Values for Rc and Lc,
- Values for plot in Fig. 4,
- Values for plot in Fig. 6